

DELVING THE ANGER MANAGEMENT OF TEACHERS

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Abstract

This study was purportedly conducted to shed light on the inmost emotional struggles of the public elementary school teachers, which result in a discrete negative outcome of buildup anger. This explicitly exhibits that anger consists of concoctions of emotional dispositions and a mental construct. This research also investigated in greater depth the coping mechanisms employed by the teachers and how the school heads address the mentors' anger management issues. The qualitative phenomenological method was utilized in the study to underpin the ten teachers' experiential accounts. From the results, this study garnered remarkable clinched that children's misbehavior was the most dominant reason that triggered the mentors into mental disarray and turned them into red fuming tomatoes. Teachers were able to manage their anger by moving out from their classrooms, staying calm, and taking slow deep breaths. The school heads instituted developmental programs to eradicate the teachers' anger predicaments. The outcome of the study displayed that mentors' managing their anger is imperative to bring about a more synergetic and harmonious relationship between and among the pivotal actors of the learning environment.

Introduction

According to Mark Twain (n.d.), —Anger is an acid that can do more harm to the vessel in which it is stored than to anything on which it is poured.‡ This adage superimposed that anger is an unprecedented manifestation of emotional

discord, which could cause internal harm to the person, not the event or the person that provoked the wrath. In brighter light, anger is a concoction of an emotional disposition and a mental construct. Emotions emerge only as a response to the individual's appraisal of the event as meaningful and important (1), which suggests that it is not the event itself that causes the emotion, but the individual's appraisal (2).

Myriads of the researchers have claimed that anger has been adjudged as the most prominent among the teachers' professional lives (3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8). Teachers, especially at the elementary level, have been experiencing frequent pep-up emotions due to the uncanny misdemeanors of the pupils. This could negatively impact the teachers' concentration and the effectiveness of the execution of the planned activities for the class. Even how eager they were to suppress their anger; it manifests itself to some degree. According to Buric et al. (3), some of the emotion regulation strategies used by teachers to regulate their anger (e.g., suppression or hiding feelings) can negatively influence their professional well-being, sense of efficacy, and teaching quality.

However, this perception runs counter to the ideology embarked on by Octaviano (9) when he argued that feeling angry is normal. According to him, anger is an emotional experience at one time or another. It is part of life. It is a reaction to an emotion and not a planned action. It is learned; thus, it can be unlearned. It is not curable and should not be treated as such. This is also paralleled to other advocacies which take into account the idea that anger is an emotion that is often created by the discrepancy between our expectations and our reality (10). It should not always be considered a negative emotion.

It is a healthy and natural emotion that should be explored, not suppressed (11); this is in conjunction with the idea of Garcia (12), who specifies that anger is a normal, healthy emotion. Still, at the tail end of the spectrum, it is insalubrious if it occurs in a very uncontrollable manner.

Though anger is a normal display of emotional outbursts, the school in the Philippines are advocating proper execution and implementation of the DepEd Order 40 series of 2012, which is called the Child Protection Policy. A program to give exceptional protection to children and teenagers under the age of 18 who are badly threatened or endangered by circumstances that interfere with their normal development and over which they have no influence, as well as to support the relevant agencies in their rehabilitation. In so doing, DepEd shall ensure that schools are a safe place for the education of children. The best interest of the child shall be the paramount consideration in all decisions and actions involving children and will uphold in all possible ways, zero-tolerance policy for any act of child abuse, exploitation, violence, discrimination, bullying, and other forms of abuse. Abuse includes but is not limited to physical abuse, derogatory words, emotional abuse, and mental torture.

With this in mind, private and public schools ensure that all teachers are well informed on properly internalizing the science of managing their anger. "Prevention is better than cure," as the saying goes. Being able to predict what situations will be the cause anger is a tremendous tool in helping the teachers keep their temper at the cranial level.

In its agreeable sense, anger management refers to the process which could help people identify stressors; people learn steps to help them stay calm. They may handle tense situations in a constructive, positive way (23). It's also a process of recognizing when one's anger is starting to spread or manifesting itself, and then taking steps to calm down and deal with the problem in a good manner" (24). An

anger management program in a school does not prevent anyone from having an anger episode; it teaches them how to handle their anger in an appropriate way (11).

Anger management also aims to assist a person in reducing their anger. It reduces the emotional and physical arousal that anger can cause. However, a person can learn to regulate their reactions and respond in a socially acceptable way (23). It is a systematic method of cognitively recognizing that getting rid of anger is not imperative, but it enhances life. People can look at the purposes of anger in both positive and negative lights. Hence, the true goal of anger management is not to suppress feelings of anger but rather to understand the message behind the emotion and express it healthily without losing control (12).

Teachers are an important element in the learning process. They are the cornerstone in the learners' growth of knowledge and wisdom and are the front liners to the successful and holistic development of the child. Therefore, it is of great import that they have to be accorded or laid on the best possible modes of adaptation to handle their stress and anger inside the classroom to make the studentteacher relationship more harmonic and symbiotic.

The research will try to examine the vital role of anger management within educational environments. The works of Chen(34) Tang et al (35) Valinasab and Zeinali(36) had examined the positive emotions will facilitate the transition of student-centered teaching and motivation.. The works You and Kang(37) Xie and Guo(38) highlighted the role of emotions and mindfulness in regulating learning, with students' emotional regulation influencing their learning approach and vice versa. These studies recommended that teacher and peer support, combined with mindfulness practices, play a significant role in cultivating positive academic emotions which it might be practiced by the teachers that the researchers of this paper are interested in.

From the foregoing clusters of ideal thoughts, this study has evolved. First, to dissect cautiously the reasons why elementary teachers have had anger episodes. Second, to investigate in depth the coping strategies used to minimize the primary elementary

teachers' pep-up emotions. And lastly, to scrutinize how the school administrators are attuned in managing their teacher's anger incidents and how they are helping them deal with these uncanny and, most of the time, spur-of-the-moment anger manifestations.

Methodology

This study purportedly uncovered the provocative reasons for teachers' anger episodes inside the classrooms, coping mechanisms to combat anger, and the move of the school heads to address the anger management problem issues of the teachers in Baguio City. Thus, this undertaking embraced the qualitative method of research specifically exploited the phenomenological approach. This qualitative approach showcased the actual voices of the participants on the aforementioned problems under study.

The respondents of the study were selected public-school teachers who are presently teaching at the elementary level. The teachers are affiliated to 10 selected public schools which hosted the largest population of students in the city.

The purposive sampling technique was primarily used as an inclusion criterion in the selection of the respondents. Eighteen (18) mentors were purposively handpicked and were interviewed via chat and personal calls.

The main data instrumentation employed in the study was based on a semi-structured interview guide formulated by the researchers with the aid of their research consultants. The interview guide consisted of two parts: The first part delineated the demographic profiles of the respondents as to name and the school affiliation. The second part comprised the interview questions that lay the groundwork for this endeavor: 1) What are the reasons that trigger your anger inside the classroom? 2) What coping mechanism did you use to manage your anger 3) How does your school head address the anger management of teachers.

Prior to the execution of the one-on-one interview using a digital platform and phone call

sessions to the respondents, the researchers first solicited the approval of the informants that she may be allowed to conduct an interview session.

After granting permission, the researchers openly disclosed the purpose and aim of the study, and the participants were assured that their comments would remain anonymous, and that data would be treated with confidentiality, respect, and privacy. Resultant of the consolidation of the needed data, the researchers transcribed it verbatim and presented it in tabular form based on narrative format.

To obtain reliable, systematic, and valid results on the present qualitative investigation, the researchers clustered all the uniform responses and presented them in a more understandable manner. All the lived contexts and experiences of the teachers were recorded and tabulated.

Results and Discussions

The researchers exhausted all possible means until data saturation was achieved. Eighteen (18) teachers from the different public schools in Baguio City willingly answered the interview questions.

Reasons that trigger the anger episode of the teacher

It was shown on the table that the highest and most pressing factor that triggers the anger episodes of the teachers in selected public schools in Baguio City is the misdemeanor of the students. The problem indicators include the perceived elevated levels of inattentiveness, classroom disturbances, or disciplinary problems. This was well-reinforced by some of the respondents when they sighed:

—Pupils who are not listening or not paying attention, some are busy talking to their seatmate, during group activities (Teacher B and C., Personal Communication, March 21, 2021).

According to Shek (25), student misbehaviors such as disruptive talking, chronic avoidance of work, clowning, interfering with teaching activities, harassing classmates, verbal insults, rudeness to teacher, defiance, and hostility are thorny issues in the everyday classroom. Teachers typically claimed that these unsettling classroom behaviors were uncomfortable, stressful, and that they had to devote

a significant amount of time and energy to managing the classroom. Obviously, student misbehaviors retard the smoothness and effectiveness of teaching and impede the student's learning along with his/her classmates.

Problem	Responses
Event/behaviors that trigger the anger of the teacher in public school.	1.. Misbehavior (5)
	2. Do not submit requirements on time or no output
	3. Disrespectful
	4. Overload work
	5. Irritated on a high pitch and hard voice of the learner
	6. Other forms of unruly behavior like vandalism and not fixing books.

Table 1. Reasons that trigger the anger episode of the teachers.

According to Yussif (26), there are so many reasons why students misbehave in class. These are often due to the following factors:

a) student:

1. Impulsivity
2. Personal skill deficiency
3. Belief deficiency while on the part of the

(B) Teacher

1. Failure to teach effectively
2. Inaccurate expectations
3. Inaccurate judgment and

(c) environmental/societal factors

1. Family
2. Sociability
3. Other responsibilities/work.

Toshalis (27), on his end, widened its concept and defined misbehavior as a form of communication. According to him, it is how messages were sent to others that something is not good. In his words, he explicitly described the nuances of misbehavior, —All of us—adults

and youth alike—tend to misbehave whenever we find ourselves in circumstances that threaten our well-being. We are more likely to act out when we feel defenseless, misunderstood, embarrassed, or betrayed. It happens in families at the dinner table, at faculty meetings, and in classrooms."

Reasons that trigger the anger episode of the teacher

Reflected in table 2 are the coping strategies employed by the teachers to tame their emotional upsurges. It was worthy to note that along with this problem, the teachers used the inhale and exhale technique and classroom getaway modem to alienate themselves from the tumultuous scenario inside the class. This is an intellectual move knowing that spending time outside and breathing fresh air can help relieve their anger, improve their mood, and contemplate the best ways to release unresolved conflicts by reevaluating what transpired. This is a therapy in itself because teachers as humans could more often construct and permeate sharp decision-making capabilities in the great outdoors.

Table 2. Coping mechanisms of teachers.

Coping Mechanism	Responses
Strategies used to combat anger management issues	1. Going outside the classroom to calm down, deep breath or breathing exercises (6)
	2. Keep quiet and give them exercises or activities to answer
	3. Divert my attention to other things so that I will not hurt my pupils verbally and physically
	4. I pray a lot; I start telling a story before the lesson, bring out the kids, do action songs and exercises, and quote encouraging verses from the bible.

According to Better Health (28), people who are stressed are more likely to experience anger. Several research from around the world have shown that regular breathing and physical activity can help to boost mood and reduce stress. This could be due to the fact that physical activity consumes stress hormones while also increasing the production of mood-regulating neurotransmitters like endorphins and catecholamines in the brain. The result of the study is also concurrently affirmed by Mayo (29) when he stressed that —timeouts are not just for

kids. Allow yourself to take short breaks during stressful periods of the day. A few moments of silence may help you feel more prepared to deal with what's coming up without becoming irritated or furious. "He added, —when your temper flares, put relaxation skills to work. Deep breathing exercises, envisioning a serene environment, or repeating a calming word or phrase, such as "Take it easy," are all effective relaxation techniques, as are listening to music, writing in a journal, or practicing a few yoga poses - whatever it takes to help you relax."

Letendre (30) recommends techniques on ways to cope with anger management issues. He readily admits that understanding the cycle of rage is critical so that teachers and anger management group facilitators can plan ahead to avoid clashes. School staff may be able to break the cycle of anger by recognizing and understanding the many stages of anger before the situation spirals out of control if they recognize and understand the various stages of anger. Esterline (11) supplemented the foregoing contention and exemplified that teachers and school social workers have to be aware of the individual student's patterns and how they use aggression; this could assist and help them break the cycle. The student can be taught how to deal with their feelings more constructively. Children can learn more productive ways of handling their anger through anger management.

School Heads Ways of Addressing Anger Management Issues

Depicted in Table 3 are the ways by which the school head channel the anger management issues of teachers. It was revealed that among the markers, the teachers unanimously agreed that the administrator used the In-Service Training (INSET) as a platform to disseminate important reforms or changes. They also used this as an essential vehicle or driving force for teachers to reevaluate some of their personality and character issues that they may need to improve. This momentous undertaking like INSET seminars and lecture fora could also benefit the school and the students. According

to Omar (31), In-service training acts as a catalyst for teachers' effectiveness. It is also a way of updating teachers' skills and knowledge to improve teaching and learning, leading to better job performance. Teachers need in-service training to meet new problems and changes in the educational sector. Inservice training is also an important component of enhancing teacher professionalism. In-service training must be effective in order for teachers to utilize their newfound knowledge in the classroom. The administrator's position, instructors' attitudes, training needs, and in-service training methodologies are all aspects that influence the efficacy of in-service training.

Table 3. School heads ways of addressing anger management Issues of teachers.

Action	Responses
Addressing anger management by the school heads	1. Anger management issues will be one of the topics in INSET
	2. Remind the teacher about the —No touch Policy and Child Protection Policy of the Department of Education.
	3. Continuous infusion of maximum tolerance

Rated second among the indicators is the item, continuous reminder on the teachers about the —No touch Policy and Child Protection Policy of the Department of Education. To confirm this contention, one teacher exclaimed:

Our school head always reminds us of the NoTouch Policy and Child Protection Policy. He always tells us to control ourselves because we will always be on the losing end (Teacher L. , personal communication, March 22, 2021).

The teaching workforce and the administrator have been given a responsibility to take care of the children's welfare. This was well promulgated not only by virtue of DepEd's Child Protection Policy (32) but also by the Children Act of 1989. An act that prescribes the paramount importance of children's welfare and undue delay may likely prejudice the well-being and safety of the child. With this critical standpoint, the Department of Education has ascribed accountability to the educational sectors, teachers, and administrators alike to place increasing responsibilities upon their

respective domains to be proactive in child protection.

There are many ways that anger could be controlled and could be eradicated in a more manageable form. In the studies conducted on anger management, it was observed that this concept was based on many factors, and different intervention approaches were used in accordance with conglomerate perspectives. Kellner and Bry (13) state that anger management training generally involves three stages. The first is to provide information about anger's cognitive and behavioral components. There could be problems resulting from the unpredictable flow of emotional energy. However, education does not exclude the controlled release of our emotions' energy, i.e., it does not prevent them from being felt (22). Some studies in the literature emphasize the effectiveness of the cognitive-behavioral approach in anger management training (14; 15; 16; 17; 18; 19, 20). The most important point among the characteristics of anger that researchers emphasize is that it is possible to learn about anger expressions and their style and select more appropriate and positive rather than dwelling on negative anger expressions containing aggressive elements (21). There may be issues that develop from the erratic flow of emotional energy. However, education does not prohibit the release of our emotions' energy in a controlled manner, i.e., it does not prevent them from being experienced (22).

Conclusions

This study has been so much engrossed in unleashing the inmost emotional upsurges of the teachers and how well they control these pep-up emotions. From the investigative pieces of evidence collected, it was determined that the misbehavior of children was the most dominant reason that triggered their mentors into disarray and turned them into red fuming tomatoes. Public elementary school teachers were able to manage their anger by moving out from their classrooms, staying calm, and taking slow deep breaths. The school heads felt that seminars and developmental programs could minimize and

eradicate the anger management problems of the teachers. The outcome of the study displayed that mentors' managing their anger is imperative to bring about a dichotic relationship between teachers and students and create a warm learning atmosphere.

With an evolving perspective and brighter frame of reference that anger management could be achieved, the study recommends that the teachers have to devise activities that could stimulate the students' interest to an elevated level. This is a good way to divert the students' attention and minimize misdemeanors or misbehaviors inside the classroom. The more the students are busy, the less likely they are to create disruptive behaviors. Giving them challenging tasks will arouse their mental processes, and they will have no time to engage in unwarranted activities that can spark or cause the teachers' emotional upsurges. As Serin (2019) concurred, the cognitive-behavioral approach used in the implemented curriculum reduces anger and aggressive behaviors. It is also indispensably needed that there be an infusion of more character and personality-building seminars to continuously inculcate to the faculty members the benefits of self-care vis-à-vis their students' welfare. Lastly, school administrators have to use a healthier alternative to release all the build-in pepup emotions of the teachers in a more productive way. In sculpting and imbibing a more synergetic relationship and bond among the pivotal actors of the academe, a yearly summer getaway could be fun to engage in.

Author contributions

The corresponding author and the co-author, have shared concerted efforts in the pursuit of the study from the conceptualization to the research writeup; data collection, data analysis, or interpretation of data; and all the way to the completion of the study.

Competing interests

—The authors declared they have no conflict of interest.¶

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